
BE ON THE RIGHT PATH: BUILD YOUR E-PORTFOLIO AND BE A PROFICIENT LIBRARIAN

Ms. Mrunalini Dhondiram Gadade¹ & Dr. Shalini R. Lihitkar²

¹Librarian, Christ College, Pune.

²Professor, Department of Library & Information Science, Rashtrasant Tukdoji Maharaj Nagpur University, Nagpur.

Corresponding Author - Ms. Mrunalini Dhondiram Gadade

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7203876

Abstract:

The librarian is responsible for a diverse variety of ever-changing tasks that are frequently poorly documented. This problem can be resolved for librarians on the tenure-track or who are looking for work by creating an academic portfolio that serves as a record of their work in librarianship, achievements, awards, roles and responsibilities. E-portfolio gives motivation for continuous professional development. E-portfolio is the tool which provides a platform to create self e-identity. This paper outlines how librarians can create a personal professional e-portfolio. Which attributes can be added in the librarian e-portfolio to showcase skills and ability to become proficient librarian.

Keyword: E-portfolio; Continuous professional development; Librarian.

Introduction:

We live in an age where we are constantly gaining new knowledge, skills and educational degrees, whether formally or informally. It might be difficult to keep track of all the continuing education opportunities and certificates available. On the other hand, working in a library is a thankless and difficult profession. It can, however, be immensely lucrative. Working in a library is challenging at times, but it can also be rewarding when viewed in a different light. For bridging the gap between achievements and work pressure and prove yourself as a proficient employee we have to take help from technology. There are various resources available to assist librarians in maintaining their abilities, such as an e-portfolio. “The new library will be a place where personnel and facilities are available to

support faculty in the creation of digitized teaching materials” (Stoffle & Williams, 1995). An e-portfolio is a digital collection of papers that demonstrate your librarianship skills and expertise. Because it allows you to see yourself from a different perspective, creating an e-portfolio can be advantage to your professional development, career planning, and job hunt. E-portfolio may be used to keep track of your education and training, previous jobs, software skill sets, work experience, résumé, and personal hobbies - basically anything that will help you better understand who you are as a separator and what you bring to the table. Employers, institutes, and different authorities need to know more about candidates' soft skills, such as communication skills, leadership potential, and adaptability under pressure

— characteristics that are difficult to assess or read on paper alone.

What Is E-Portfolio?

A compilation of your work that showcases your talents and abilities is called an e-portfolio. Finding new opportunities depends on it. It's your traditional portfolio in digital form. An e-portfolio is a computer-based version of a paper-based portfolio that includes visuals, audio, video, and interactive components. It gives hiring managers a central location to view all of your work. It can also be a fantastic tool to show potential employers your talents and abilities. "Electronic portfolios are being used by elementary, secondary and college educators to lead their classrooms toward learner-centered rather than teaching-centered learning environments" (Hewett, 2004).

Ravet, S. (2005) mentioned e-portfolio definition, according to the National to the National Learning Infrastructure Initiative (US), an e-portfolio is a "a collection of authentic and diverse evidence, drawn from a larger archive representing what a person or organisation has learned over time on which the person or organisation has learn over time on which the person or organisation has reflected and designed for presentation to one or more audiences for a particular rhetorical purpose". A portfolio is a well-organized collection of materials that illustrates a person's abilities, work, and professional development (Saunders, 2003).

Professional E-Portfolio:

Professional e-portfolios, also known as Career e-portfolios, are representative artifacts that people build to show off their greatest work in order to encourage self-reflection and peer

assessment. Through the improvement in professional career, this procedure closes the assessment cycle. This professional e-portfolio is implemented in different fields like medical, arts, teacher education etc. Implementation in the field of library will give a clear picture of library personnel's.

Librarian's E-Portfolio:

The necessity for the e-portfolio determines how the e-portfolio is organised. "Librarians teaching philosophy reflects their beliefs about education and its connection with librarianship" (Lally & Trejo, 2019) The employer's needs should be the main influence on the e-portfolio's content if the librarian is utilising it as a job-hunting tool. However, the portfolio should be organised around the librarian's present, post function and emphasize how effectively the librarian meets his or her job criteria if the librarian is utilising the portfolio to conduct their yearly review evaluation or for their promotion and tenure process. In the field of education mainly teaching, research and service are the main factors in organisation of e-portfolio. But in the library field teaching is not the main job of librarians, so the organisation criteria for librarians, which may include employees' performance, professional service, or research, differ depending on the type of institution and, in some cases, even within the same institution. The librarianship portfolio must therefore detail what each librarian does in their current roles, in a manner similar to that of annual evaluations, and identify the areas of expertise in which each librarian has skills, such as reference, liaison, collection development, instruction, administration/coordination, cataloguing, and acquisitions. While governing all of the librarians' entries, this subdivision also gave them a way to set

themselves apart from not only other academic departments or institutions but also from other librarians working in the same library.

A librarian's time, effort, and contemplation on what they consider to be significant about their accomplishments are all necessary for the building and upkeep of a librarianship portfolio. The librarian must reflect on their effectiveness and how their performance and professional growth develop as a librarian in the library profession.

Functions of Librarian E-Portfolio:

- The portfolio should convey a clear picture of your professional growth as a librarian.
- The portfolio should allow the librarian the chance to explain the part their work had in their professional development, especially if they showed that they advanced in the field of librarianship in a deliberate manner. The librarian should discuss the part their work played in their professional development in their portfolio, especially if they showed.
- The portfolio should serve as a useful tool to demonstrate how you have contributed to the advancement of the library profession as well as your department and college.
- The establishment and upkeep of an academic portfolio can be helpful for librarians as a tool for job searching, as documentation to support performance appraisal or promotion and tenure review, and as a personal reflection tool to stimulate professional development and career progress.

Role of Librarians E-Portfolio:

E-portfolio in continuous professional development:

An excellent tool for continuing professional development is a librarian's e-portfolio. You can keep track of your progress, consider the abilities you have acquired, and record the projects you have worked on. Your e-portfolio can be used to list any training programmes or certificates you have finished. This will enable you to keep tabs on your development and pinpoint your strengths and flaws. It's crucial to monitor your development so you can spot problem areas and implement corrections. An effective tool for showing your abilities and expertise to potential employers is a librarian's e-portfolio. On your e-portfolio, you can list any pertinent projects and educational experiences. The users, colleagues, library professionals, authorities will find your CV to be more fascinating and compelling as a result. Employers appreciate learning that you are self-starting and have kept a record of your efforts. Applying for higher education, projects and scholarships might be facilitated by an electronic portfolio.

E-portfolio as showcase tool:

The Librarian e-portfolio also worked as a showcase tool that helped dispel some falsehoods and challenged the preconceptions of the negative role of the librarian, as a librarian working in a field beset by unjust archaic prejudices. The majority of librarians nowadays are quite tech-savvy and use cutting-edge services to help others. Librarians can plan to use the e-portfolio format as a kind of marketing "technology tool" that would promote not just librarian's abilities but also some of the technical successes and improvements of the College's library when they chose it as a promotion tool. It exhibited not just technological

abilities but also the library's involvement in a round-the-clock live chat service, the development of online library research courses to help students with their needs, and the use of social media to advertise library services. Librarian's lengthy list of duties as a faculty librarian may be found in a traditional CV or portfolio. These duties were not only highlighted in an e-portfolio, but they were also prominently displayed by incorporating links to video clips, social networking projects, and actual online tutorials.

E-portfolio for self-identity:

Self-e-identity is another crucial application of e-portfolios. It is a tool that enables you to consider your unique identity and qualities. It allows you to keep track of your talents, interests, and ambitions in addition to your passions and interests. Your leadership abilities and skills can be documented in your e-portfolio. It enables you to consider the kind of leader you are and want to be. You can use it to keep track of your extracurricular activities and charity work as well.

Cumulative Role of E-portfolio:

During tenure-track years at the College, e-portfolio functioned as a comprehensive collection of all the requirements librarians have to meet. It also monitors individuals' growth as a librarian and faculty member at the College. This form of electronic portfolio, according to Hewett (2004), is a collection of documentation that demonstrates progress toward meeting predetermined standards. The e-portfolio serves as documentation and a cumulative file to show that the specific competencies required for tenure at the college want to meet. It can detail collection development responsibilities and how, during individuals tenure-track years, librarians

worked with teaching staff from various disciplines.

E-portfolio improves your CV:

Your CV can be enhanced by using the e-portfolio. You can provide examples of your work, such as digital samples, pictures, or summaries of initiatives in which you were involved. You can use this to demonstrate your abilities, information, and experience. The content you can put in your CV is frequently rather constrained, whereas the stuff you can add to an e-portfolio is typically not.

E-portfolio for feedback on your work:

You can get feedback on your work using the e-portfolio. You can set up a place where you can get comments on your projects, presentations, and writing. This can be a terrific approach to get input from mentors and peers. Then you can use this criticism to polish your work and advance your abilities.

E-portfolio gives opportunity to learn new abilities and information:

New knowledge and abilities can be discovered via the e-portfolio. The e-portfolio can be used as a repository for samples of your work and pertinent information. When you have more experience and want to attempt something new, you can return to these samples. This can be a fantastic method to pick up new abilities and get ideas for new endeavors.

E-portfolio gives opportunity to connect other professionals:

A person's competence, proficiency, expertise, etc. are reflected in their professional e-portfolio. To solve professional challenges, issues, it can be helpful to seek assistance from other professionals. It offers a forum for talking about and sharing current trends. E-

portfolio demonstrates the library and librarian's areas of expertise.

Research contribution
Achievements and responsibilities
Information about Library and library services
Personal Interests

Outline of librarian e-portfolio:

Personal Information
Educational qualification

Part	It includes
Personal Information	Biographical information with the position of the professional.
Educational qualification	Detailed educational qualification with research related achievements and work experience which describes librarians different roles and responsibilities in different positions and institutions.
Research contribution	Other than just research degree, contribution in research in the form of research projects, guidance in research, writings in research papers, conference papers, even research ID's which indicates research contribution collectively.
Achievements and responsibilities	Different achievements and awards gained during professional tenure and different responsibilities give a platform to librarians to show their abilities for self growth and institutions too.
Information about Library and library services	This area will help to promote library and library services. Which gives an idea about librarian's contribution in library development.
Personal Interests	Other than being a librarian, he or she is a human being with special abilities and skills. Usually which can not be shown in traditional CV, this area provides this platform to showcase another aspect of personality.

Conclusion:

For the academic librarian, building a professional portfolio opens up a world of possibilities. It can be utilised in the advancement and tenure processes in addition to job searching. Academic librarians' roles are evolving now more than ever to keep up with new technological developments, educational focuses, and increased standards of quality and competition. In addition, when budgets are slashed and more librarians start to retire, we are now experiencing a

personnel and financial crisis. Because of this, it is imperative for us to know exactly what we are capable of in our work and to be able to show proof of it through documentation. The professional portfolio might hold the key to demonstrating who we are and why we matter to people both inside and outside of libraries and how academic librarians resemble other faculty in many respects. E-portfolio will help to give a respected position in the professional community.

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